

FACULTY PERSPECTIVES ON CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS IN UPHOLDING ACADEMIC INTEGRITY AT A Y COLLEGE IN METRO MANILA

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the challenges and solutions associated with upholding academic integrity at Y College from the perspectives of its faculty members. Through a descriptive-quantitative research design involving sixty (60) faculty respondents from the Business Administration and Education departments, the study addressed specific questions related to challenges, solutions, strategies, institutional policies, and the current state of academic integrity. The survey revealed a consensus on challenges that emphasized student awareness, plagiarism detection, and communication of academic integrity policies. Faculty answers agreed on a multifaceted approach to support existing strategies and emphasize continuous professional development. Strategies employed by faculty included innovative classroom management, collaboration, moral enhancement programs, advocacy, and the use of technology for plagiarism tracking. The overall ratings of academic integrity at the institution were found to be diverse, with the majority perceiving it as "Very Good," yet a significant portion identified room for improvement. Based on the results, recommendations were formulated to enhance plagiarism detection resources, improve communication policies, prioritize professional development, foster faculty-administration collaboration, and implement a moral enhancement program.

Keywords: *Academic integrity, challenges, solutions, faculty perspectives*

INTRODUCTION

In an era marked by technological advancements and evolving educational landscapes, maintaining academic integrity remains a complex challenge for institutions worldwide. The increased availability of online resources offering unapproved assistance

to students has significantly expanded the avenues for academic dishonesty, posing a potent threat to traditional safeguards (Newton, 2018; Ison, 2020). The readily available online services dedicated to facilitating plagiarism and other unethical practices further intensify this issue (Alessio & Maurer, 2018). Understanding the perceptions of faculty regarding the difficulties related to maintaining academic integrity is vital for developing strategies to stop academic dishonesty.

As a college instructor at a higher education institute (HEI) in Metro Manila, the author regularly encounters the arduous task of upholding academic integrity, which is significantly hampered by the persistent lack of student awareness regarding the fundamental importance of ethical academic conduct. Identifying instances of plagiarism and academic dishonesty is another complex task that demands constant vigilance. Striking a balance between fostering a positive learning environment and implementing rigorous measures poses an ongoing challenge. The need for more effective communication channels and comprehensive policies to guide both faculty and students is evident.

This study delves into the specific experiences of Y College faculty in upholding academic integrity. Understanding their lived experiences, concerns, and insights is crucial for comprehending the unique dynamics and complexities influencing academic integrity in this institution. Despite the critical role faculty members play in fostering a culture of honesty, there exists a gap in understanding the nuanced challenges they encounter, and the efficacy of current strategies employed. By bridging this knowledge gap and exploring potential solutions, this research aims to contribute valuable knowledge to the ongoing discourse surrounding effective strategies for cultivating a culture of academic honesty in higher education institutions. This study seeks to bridge this gap by exploring the multifaceted dimensions of academic integrity at Y College, offering insights into the specific issues faced by faculty and potential solutions to fortify the institution's commitment to academic honesty.

Research Questions

The study investigated the challenges in upholding academic integrity and explored faculty-driven solutions for both classroom practice and institutional policy, specifically aiming to answer the following questions:

1. What is the current state of academic integrity at Y College as perceived by its faculty members?
2. What are the challenges encountered by Y College faculty in upholding academic integrity?
3. What are existing faculty-driven solutions, including classroom practices and strategies, to address these challenges and enhance academic integrity within the institution?
4. How effective are existing institutional policies and resources in supporting faculty in addressing academic integrity concerns?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive survey research design to investigate the challenges and faculty-driven solutions for upholding academic integrity at Y College. A purposive sampling technique was used to select sixty faculty members, consisting of forty (40) from the Business Administration Department and twenty (20) from the Education Department. The survey was conducted online through the Google Forms application and disseminated through a link where answers were recorded anonymously. Permission to survey the institution was obtained from the Academic Coordinator and Program Coordinator. However, the name Y College was used in the research to protect the privacy of the respondents who worked at the HEI.

To address the research objectives, a structured electronic survey was designed with a mix of closed-ended (e.g., Likert scale ratings) and open-ended questions covering faculty perspectives on challenges, solutions, classroom strategies, institutional resources, and the perceived state of academic integrity. Pilot testing with a small sample ($n = 15$) yielded a Cronbach's alpha of $\alpha = 0.97$, indicating good internal consistency. Quantitative data analysis was conducted to present descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) and provide a clear overview of the faculty's perspective.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Challenges in Upholding Academic Integrity

Faculty surveys revealed a strong consensus on challenges impeding academic integrity at Y College (Table 1). The most prominent issue identified was student unawareness, highlighting the need for targeted awareness campaigns and educational initiatives. Faculty also expressed challenges in identifying instances of plagiarism and academic dishonesty, emphasizing the importance of enhancing detection methods and providing faculty with the necessary tools and resources. Clear and well-communicated academic integrity policies also emerged as a significant concern, suggesting opportunities for improvements in communication channels, faculty training programs, and collaboration between faculty and administration.

These findings align with previous research by Guerrero-Dib et al. (2020) who suggested that addressing the identified challenges would benefit from improvements in communication channels, faculty training programs, and collaboration efforts between faculty and administration. In addition, Gow and Sun (2023) recommended that academic integrity policies should be clearly communicated to students and faculty members, and the consequences of academic dishonesty should be made explicit.

These findings not only reinforce the calls for improved communication, training, and collaboration but also reveal specific areas that require targeted attention at Y College, namely student awareness and faculty training on advanced plagiarism detection mechanisms. Addressing these identified challenges through targeted interventions and collaborative efforts has the potential to significantly improve academic integrity at Y College.

Table 1. Challenges in Upholding Academic Integrity

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The lack of awareness among students about academic integrity is a significant challenge.	4.27	Strongly Agree
2. Faculty members find it challenging to identify instances of plagiarism or cheating in student work.	4.12	Agree
3. Faculty members face difficulties in identifying and addressing instances of academic dishonesty.	3.93	Agree
4. Insufficient clarity in academic integrity policies and procedures poses challenges for both faculty and students.	3.95	Agree
5. The lack of timely and effective communication about academic integrity expectations contributes to challenges in upholding integrity standards.	4.18	Agree
6. Faculty members do not receive sufficient training on promoting and upholding academic integrity.	3.57	Agree
7. Students are not generally aware of the importance of academic integrity in their academic pursuits.	3.65	Agree
8. Reporting mechanisms for academic integrity violations are not clear and not accessible to faculty members.	3.50	Agree
9. The current academic integrity policies at Y College are not effectively communicated to both faculty and students.	3.45	Agree
10. There is no effective communication and collaborative effort between faculty and administration regarding academic integrity issues.	3.53	Agree

Solutions to the Challenges in Upholding Academic Integrity as Perceived by Faculty Members

Table 2 shows the faculty perspectives on potential solutions to the challenges in upholding academic integrity at Y College. Faculty members at Y College collectively advocate for a multifaceted approach to address academic integrity concerns. The results indicate a shared belief in the effectiveness of current strategies, providing a foundation for building upon existing initiatives. The recognition of the need for ongoing professional development highlights a commitment to continuous improvement, aligning with the dynamic nature of academic integrity challenges. The data underscore the critical role of faculty training, with an emphasis on both policy implementation and comprehensive programs. The overwhelmingly strong agreement regarding the college administration's commitment to supporting faculty, the need for additional resources, and the call for increased faculty involvement in policy development collectively highlight a desire for a collaborative and supportive institutional framework.

Table 2. Solutions to the Challenges in Upholding Academic Integrity

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
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1. The strategies I currently use to address academic integrity issues are effective.	4.08	Agree
2. The college's policies and initiatives effectively contribute to promoting academic integrity.	3.77	Agree
3. I believe that ongoing professional development opportunities would enhance my ability to address academic integrity concerns.	4.08	Agree
4. Adequate training should be provided to faculty regarding the implementation of academic integrity policies.	4.18	Agree
5. The college administration should demonstrate a commitment to supporting faculty in promoting academic integrity.	4.37	Strongly Agree
6. Additional resources and support are needed to enhance faculty efforts in upholding academic integrity.	4.23	Strongly Agree
7. More comprehensive training programs on academic integrity would be beneficial for faculty members.	4.22	Strongly Agree
8. Increased awareness campaigns and educational initiatives are required to foster a culture of academic integrity.	4.23	Strongly Agree
9. Faculty members should have a more active role in the development of academic integrity policies.	4.28	Strongly Agree
10. More comprehensive training programs on academic integrity would be beneficial for faculty members.	4.22	Strongly Agree

Institutional Policies and Resources Currently in place to Support the Faculty in Addressing Academic Integrity

Faculty responses regarding specific college policies or initiatives for academic integrity reveal a mixed landscape. The most frequent response ("None") highlights a perceived lack of structured measures, echoed by twenty-seven (27) respondents explicitly stating no policies exist. While three respondents chose not to comment, potentially due to unfamiliarity, three acknowledged the existence of several policies, suggesting partial efforts. Three others pointed to the student and faculty handbook, and one highlighted the need for technical support, emphasizing the importance of providing resources and tools to facilitate the implementation of academic integrity measures. Three respondents chose not to provide comments, indicating a reluctance to discuss or a lack of awareness regarding existing policies.

The predominance of responses indicating a lack of specific policies or initiatives ("None") underscores a potential gap in the institutional framework for addressing academic integrity at Y College. The responses affirm the need for a more structured and comprehensive approach to academic integrity, potentially involving the development and dissemination of clear policies and initiatives. The mentions of s policies, referral to handbooks, and the implementation of a weekly report system demonstrate that there were preexisting efforts in place. However, the limited number of respondents citing these

initiatives suggests that there may be room for improvement in communicating and reinforcing these measures across the faculty community. The mention of technical support indicates a potential area for enhancement, emphasizing the importance of providing faculty members with the necessary resources and tools to effectively implement and enforce academic integrity policies.

In conclusion, the responses highlight the importance of clarifying, communicating, and potentially enhancing academic integrity policies and initiatives at Y College. This could contribute to a more cohesive and effective approach to upholding and promoting academic integrity across the institution.

Current State of Academic Integrity at Y College as Perceived by Faculty Members

The responses to the question regarding the overall rating of the current state of academic integrity at Y College provide a snapshot of faculty perceptions. The results are summarized as follows: Good (14 respondents); Very Good (25 respondents); Poor (15 respondents); and Fair (6 respondents). The largest proportion of respondents rated the state as "Very Good," suggesting a positive assessment of the institution's efforts in upholding academic integrity. On the other hand, a notable number of respondents rated the current state as either "Poor" or "Fair," indicating a significant portion of faculty members perceived room for improvement in the existing academic integrity framework. Understanding the factors influencing these diverse perceptions is crucial for the institution to address any existing challenges effectively. This might involve further investigation into specific concerns raised by those who rated the state as "Poor" or "Fair," as well as gathering feedback on areas that are contributing to the positive assessments from those who rated it as "Good" or "Very Good."

Conclusions

The findings of this study offered valuable insights into the challenges and solutions related to academic integrity at Y College.

The identified challenges, such as the lack of student awareness, difficulties in plagiarism detection, and inadequate communication of policies, underscored the complex nature of maintaining academic honesty within the institution.

Faculty perspectives on the solutions to these challenges revealed a consensus on the need for ongoing professional development, administrative support, and more comprehensive training programs. The emphasis on collaboration, innovative teaching methods, and technological solutions suggested a multifaceted approach to address the identified issues effectively. However, the acknowledgment of a lack of specific policies or initiatives by a substantial number of faculty members raised concerns about the institutional framework for promoting academic integrity. The varying perceptions of the current state of academic integrity, ranging from "Very Good" to "Poor," indicated a diverse landscape of opinions among faculty members. The study highlighted the importance of a holistic and collaborative approach to enhancing academic integrity at Y College.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher put forward the following recommendations:

1. The educational institution should provide additional resources and support for faculty members to enhance plagiarism detection efforts. Consider investing in advanced plagiarism detection tools and training programs to improve faculty proficiency in identifying and addressing instances of plagiarism.
2. Educators should improve communication policies on academic integrity by establishing clear and accessible channels for disseminating information, such as an updated handbook or an online portal, ensuring that everyone is well-informed about expectations and consequences.
3. The institution should prioritize ongoing professional development opportunities for faculty members. Offer workshops, seminars, and training sessions focused on academic integrity, innovative teaching methods, and effective communication strategies. This continuous learning approach would ensure that the faculty remained well-equipped to manage evolving challenges.
4. The administration should facilitate regular communication and collaboration with the faculty regarding academic integrity issues. Establish forums or committees where faculty members could actively participate in the development and improvement of policies, fostering a sense of shared responsibility.
5. The institution should consider the implementation of a moral enhancement program to instill ethical values among students. This program could be a

great integration into the curriculum, providing students with opportunities for moral and character development throughout their academic journey.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The key issues involved in the conduct of this study were the respondents' right to confidentiality, right to fair treatment, and informed consent.

Informed Consent. Before releasing the study to participants, approval was obtained from the Academic Coordinator and Program Coordinator of the Y College. Participants were sent a letter of invitation containing the following:

1. A brief description of the purpose of the study.
2. A brief description of the content of the questionnaire.
3. Eligibility criteria for participants of the study.

Participants were asked to sign an informed consent form. They were made aware of the right to withdraw their participation at any point (including during the survey) until their responses were anonymously recorded. The researcher's contact information was included in the invitation letter for any clarification or withdrawal requests.

Right to Confidentiality of Information. Completed questionnaires were recorded anonymously into a database worksheet. The collection form did not include any identifying information such as full name, contact information, email address, or location. Access to collated anonymous data was limited to the researcher only.

Right to Fair Treatment. The eligibility of participants was strictly based on the set criteria and the study's requirements. All invited participants were fairly treated regardless of acceptance, refusal, or withdrawal from the study. There was no offensive, abusive, non-inclusive, or discriminatory language included in the questionnaire and letter of invitation. The researcher accommodated participants with special needs and maintained sensitivity to diverse beliefs and cultures.

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